

Highly efficient decontamination of nerve agent sarin surrogate DMMP using the novel NiFe₂O₄/NaY-type zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent

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ABSTRACT

In this work, NiFe₂O₄/NaY-type zeolite nanocomposite was manufactured by the hydrothermal strategy and subsequently characterized via FE-SEM, EDX, EDX dot mapping, FTIR, XRD and VSM techniques. The decontamination of nerve agent sarin surrogate dimethyl methyl phosphonate (DMMP) was then conducted over the as-synthesized NiFe₂O₄/NaY-type zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent from water media using ³¹P NMR analysis. Various physicochemical parameters, involving contact time, adsorbent dosage and initial DMMP concentration on the decontamination of DMMP nerve simulant were precisely investigated. ³¹P NMR analysis data verified that the maximum decontamination of 98.2% for DMMP. The factors obtained including contact time of 60 min, initial concentration of 60 mg/L and adsorbent dose of 50 mg were considered as the optimal amounts for the decontamination reaction. Finally, methyl phosphoric acid (MPA) as the harmless degradation product of DMMP on the NiFe₂O₄/NaY-type zeolite nanocomposite was emerged and recognized.

Keywords: NiFe₂O₄/NaY, zeolite, nanocomposite, adsorbent, decontamination, DMMP, MPA.